

USING FAIRY TALES TO ENHANCE COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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Abstract. *Using fairy tales to enhance comprehension skills provides an effective and engaging approach to developing critical reading abilities. Fairy tales, with their simple yet captivating plots, distinct characters, and moral lessons, offer an ideal platform for practicing key comprehension strategies.*

Key words: *prediction, inference, character analysis, plot structure, setting, conflict, resolution, theme, moral lesson, vocabulary building, sequencing, retelling, critical thinking, comparing versions.*

Using fairy tales to enhance comprehension skills is a creative and effective approach, especially for younger readers. Fairy tales have unique narrative structures, vivid characters, and universal themes that can help improve a range of reading comprehension skills. Here are several strategies for using fairy tales to enhance comprehension:

Predicting and Inferencing

Before reading: Ask students to predict what might happen based on the title or the cover of the book.

During reading: Encourage students to make inferences about characters' motivations, emotions, or the outcome of events based on textual clues.

After reading: Discuss whether their predictions were correct and why or why not. This helps with making logical conclusions based on the text.

Character Analysis

Identify key characters: Focus on the main characters (e.g., the hero, villain, sidekick, etc.) and explore their traits, motivations, and changes throughout the story.

Character mapping: Students can create character maps that detail the characters' relationships and transformations during the story, which helps them track development and improve understanding of plot structure.

Identifying Story Elements

Fairy tales typically have a clear structure with specific elements:

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Setting: Where and when does the story take place? How does the setting influence the plot?

Conflict: What is the main problem or challenge the protagonist faces?

Resolution: How is the problem solved? What lesson is learned?

Have students fill out a story map or diagram, identifying the main elements to help them comprehend how the plot unfolds.

Theme Exploration

Discuss universal themes: Fairy tales often revolve around timeless themes like good vs. evil, kindness rewarded, and justice. After reading, engage students in discussing the underlying moral or lesson of the tale.

Compare themes: Students can compare the themes of different fairy tales to see how they are presented similarly or differently. For example, compare the themes of "Cinderella" and "Snow White."

Vocabulary Building

Fairy tales often include rich and descriptive language. Have students highlight unfamiliar words, then discuss the meanings based on context.

Word studies: Focus on specific words or phrases used in the fairy tale and explore their meanings and connotations.

Word maps: Have students create word maps for important or new vocabulary, showing the word's definition, synonyms, antonyms, and a sentence using the word.

Sequencing and Retelling

Story sequencing: After reading a fairy tale, students can work to put events from the story in order. This will reinforce their understanding of the plot structure and how events lead to one another.

Retelling the story: Encourage students to retell the story in their own words, emphasizing the main points of the plot and character actions. This reinforces comprehension and the ability to summarize key ideas.

Critical Thinking and Discussion

Ask open-ended questions: Encourage deep thinking by asking questions such as, "What do you think would happen if the main character made a different choice?" or "Why do you think the villain did what they did?"

Debate and discussion: Fairy tales often have moral dilemmas or ambiguous elements. Engage students in debates about the characters' choices or the fairness of the resolutions.

Comparing Versions of Fairy Tales

Many fairy tales have different versions depending on the culture or retelling. Comparing these versions helps develop comprehension as students must notice similarities and differences in plot, character, or setting.

Example activity: Compare the Grimms' version of "Hansel and Gretel" with a more modern adaptation, and discuss how the changes affect the story's tone or lesson.

Using Visuals and Storyboards

Create visual representations of the story's key events. Students can draw or use digital tools to make storyboards that represent the progression of the fairy tale. This visual support can strengthen comprehension by helping students connect the events more clearly.

Creating Extensions

Alternate endings: Have students create alternative endings or imagine "what if" scenarios, which will prompt them to think critically about character motivations and plot structure.

Fairy tale mashups: Combine two different fairy tales into one story. This activity promotes creativity while allowing students to synthesize their comprehension of different narratives.

11. Comprehension Checklists

Use comprehension checklists to guide students in identifying the key points in a fairy tale (main idea, character motivations, conflicts, and resolution). This can be helpful for students to self-assess their understanding.

By engaging with fairy tales through these strategies, students can deepen their comprehension skills in a fun and accessible way, using familiar stories to explore complex literary concepts.

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